

Stochastic optimization framework for online scheduling of an EV charging station in a residential place with photovoltaics and energy storage system

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Abstract— House and building energy management systems (HEMS) are becoming key when it comes to assure grid stability and to offer flexibility. At the same time, energy systems technology has evolved to enable energy storage systems and electric vehicles to be managed together with local generated energy taking into consideration the preferences of the household owner. Contributing to this tendency, this work presents a stochastic optimization platform (SOFW) for optimal control using dynamic programming and stochastic optimization models. A stochastic optimization model involving a household composed of photovoltaics, energy storage system and an electric vehicle is designed and tested within SOFW. The uncertainties of the plug-in time and state of charge of the battery of the electric vehicle are modeled using a Markovian process and a Monte-Carlo simulation. The results showed that the proposed stochastic optimization model can be solved using dynamic programming and deployed as a continuous optimal control within SOFW. The system will be deployed shortly in Italy within one use case of the Storage4Grid (S4G) project.

Index Terms— electric vehicle charging, energy storage systems, dynamic programming, Markov processes, stochastic optimization framework

I. INTRODUCTION

The European Union has set challenging energy goals for 2030, 40% reduction of greenhouse gas emission and at least a 27% share of renewable energy consumption [1]. Energy management locally at households or buildings, as well as aggregated in the communities plays an important role on the way to achieving these goals. Smart metering and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies are to become enablers of energy management. Thus, energy data is increasingly available based on the communication capabilities of smart meters, whereupon it can be made available whenever and wherever needed through IoT technologies [2].

Moreover, these technologies, due to available information and communication channels, unfold a variety of control possibilities, which set the ground to a higher penetration of

renewables. As energy production based on renewables depends on weather conditions and because grid instability caused by this dependency has to be avoided, new ways of handling the generated power are to be investigated. Thus, maximizing the consumption of own-generated energy transforms consumers into self-sustained prosumers and is one measure towards enhancing grid stability. In fact, the surplus power produced by renewables is used to charge energy storage systems (ESS), optimizing local consumption and contributing to grid stability.

In addition, increasing amounts of electric vehicles means extra uncertain load to the grid. The load is considered uncertain because of the random charging and driving profiles. Considering a home energy management system (HEMS), EV charging schedules need to be integrated into it, so that certain optimization criteria are fulfilled.

The online optimal local control of energy flow in a HEMS including the uncertainty introduced by EVs is what we are focusing on in this work. We propose a stochastic optimization framework (SOFW) using dynamic programming to solve a stochastic optimization model, which is also defined in this work.

In the literature, several contributions deal with HEMS. Some works are related to demand management systems where loads are shifted to limit the household peak demand while applying user preferences [3][4]. Other works are related to energy management including EV charging and discharging to the grid [5]. Similarly, discrete optimization models are used for the optimal management of electrical loads including EVs in residential use cases. In [6] for example, the author uses dynamic tariffs for optimizing energy costs while controlling shiftable, interruptible and thermostatic loads. As we can see, HEMS approaches differ from each other and try to control the power supplied to some household electrical devices. Other contributions schedule the optimal charging of EVs using heuristic algorithms such as genetic algorithms or grey wolf optimization algorithms [7][8]. Nevertheless, heuristic algorithms present multiple results for an optimization problem,

which makes it unsuitable for online optimal control as the one presented in this work. Moreover, Markovian processes have been used for managing energy resources in a residential building including EVs [9]. The stochasticity of weather-dependent and controllable loads as well as of charging of EVs is included through Markov models. For EVs, three states are analyzed: charge, discharge and drive.

In summary, our contribution is twofold: it is first a new approach for modelling uncertainties using real-time data, and secondly it introduces a stochastic optimization framework. The latter is able to continuously generate the optimal control for ESS and for charging station of an EV within a HEMS whereby the charging uncertainty model is applied.

The next sections will describe the use case within the Storage4Grid project, the approach followed to design the SOFW, model the uncertainties and define the stochastic optimization model, the implementation of SOFW and the stochastic optimization model, the test scenarios and results.

II. USE CASE SPECIFICATION

This chapter presents a residential EV charging use case for the stochastic optimization framework (SOFW) that is developed for the S4G project. This use case focusses on residential houses with photovoltaics generation (PV) and energy storage system (ESS), which can export the surplus generation to the electricity grid, as well as, import power from it, as shown in Fig. 1. In this use case, the owner of the household is an energy prosumer who drives daily an electric vehicle (EV) back and forth to work and prefers to charge the EV at home. It is important to note that the EV battery is not used for generation purposes i.e. within a vehicle-to-grid (V2G) scheme.

The residential EV charging optimization model aims at charging the EV solely according to the local energy management targets, which excludes the interests of other entities in the energy market, such as power network or other consumers. Thus, self-consumption, PV utilization and profit maximization of the household owner have been set as optimization criteria. Furthermore, charging at home should be preferred and it is used as a restriction within the optimization model. For this reason, we included a term that penalizes away-charging, which will occur when the home charging fails to meet daily driving distances. The optimization model for residential EV charging assumes high accuracy of weather, demand and electricity price forecast. However, due to the uncertainty of the driving behavior, EV battery's discharge profile is stochastic.

Both the optimization model presented and a stochastic optimization framework used to implement the model were developed within this work. The optimization framework corresponds to an extension of the work presented in [10].

Figure 1. Use case entities of S4G project

III. APPROACH

This section will describe the stochastic optimization framework and the stochastic optimization model developed for the residential EV charging use case as well as the modeling of uncertainties related to EV's plug-in time.

A. Stochastic Optimization Framework (SOFW)

SOFW manages a Pyomo [11] optimization model and assigns inputs and outputs automatically. Parameters of the optimization model are handled as inputs, and variables as outputs. The framework enables the modeling of uncertainties, which can be calculated from the real-time input data; therefore it is called Stochastic Optimization Framework (SOFW). As the optimization is carried out continuously and an optimal solution is found for each time instant, SOFW performs as a continuous optimal controller.

Hence, a developed optimization model is entered into SOFW, where immediate control decision for residential controllable equipment i.e. PV, ESS, EV is calculated according to a constant-length prediction and optimization horizon. In other words, SOFW starts an optimization instance with real-time parameters (e.g. EV's battery SoC, EV's plug-in data, household consumption power, etc.) It calculates the required predictions for some parameters (e.g. energy demand) for the upcoming prediction horizon of typically 24 hours and solves the optimization problem represented in the respective optimization model using these parameters and predictions. The control decisions are implemented taking the first time step of the optimization results. Later, the optimization horizon is shifted to the next time instant, real-time information is updated and the process is repeated as described above.

B. Modelling the Uncertainty of EV's SoC and plug-in time

As we exclude some uncertainty factors such as demand, generation of renewables and price, the optimization model has to cope only with the stochastic charging demand, which is influenced by two interrelated uncertainty factors: plug-in profiles and EV battery's consumption profiles. Therefore, in order to design an accurate charging policy, one has to estimate when the car is away from home and how much energy the car consumes throughout the time.

The uncertainty model that we designed within this work decouples these factors based on two practical assumptions: (i) the owner drives the EV to the same destination, so energy consumption $E_{EV,daily}$ in kWh is the same every day, (ii) the time that EV spends away from the house is the same every day.

$$E_{EV,daily} = E_{EV,cap} \frac{1}{D} \sum_{d=1}^D SoC_{dep}^d - SoC_{arr}^d \quad (1)$$

The $E_{EV,daily}$ parameter is obtained by collecting data on EV's SoC levels at departure SoC_{dep}^d and arrival SoC_{arr}^d moments, calculating the daily average SoC use in D days of data and multiplying it to the EV's battery capacity $E_{EV,cap}$. Daily energy use parameter is reduced into power by using equation 2:

$$P_{EV} = \frac{E_{EV,daily}}{T_{away}} \quad (2)$$

where P_{EV} is the average discharge power from EV's battery when the EV is T_{away} units of time away from home. As result, we can conclude our assumptions into a deterministic EV' battery consumption profile:

$$P_{EV}^t = \begin{cases} P_{EV}, & t_{dep} < t < t_{arr} \\ 0, & else \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where P_{EV}^t is the power discharged from the EV's battery at the time point stated by t . This power is equal to average power consumption P_{EV} when the car is not at home, within the time period between departure t_{dep} and arrival time t_{arr} ; otherwise it is zero.

To represent the plug-in time behavior, we adopted a Markov model that captures the diurnal variation in the use of a vehicle that exhibits a stochastic plug-in pattern as presented in [12]. According to this model, EV can only attain home and away states and switch between these two states in discrete instants, see Fig. 2. Home represents the state, when the EV is plugged-in into the charging station, and away when it is unplugged.

Figure 2. Markov model for describing driving patterns

Since the probability of switching from one state to another depends on the time of day, our behavior model is an inhomogeneous Markov model. Probabilities are expressed as time-specific transition probability matrices $p(t)$, which describe the switching probabilities between two subsequent instants t and $t+1$. The elements of these matrices refer to different initial-final state pairs e.g. probability of switching from home to away state $p_{10}(t)$:

$$p(t) = \begin{bmatrix} p_{10}(t) & p_{11}(t) \\ p_{00}(t) & p_{01}(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The required data to model the transition probability matrices is a number of time series showing the states of a car within one day. These parameters are calculated by dividing the number of observed switching from home state to away state

$n_{10}(t)$ into the number of total transitions that started from home state:

$$p_{10}(t) = \frac{n_{10}(t)}{n_{10}(t) + n_{11}(t)} \quad (5)$$

C. Stochastic Dynamic Programming (SDP) Model

Controllable variables x of our optimization problem are ESS charge/discharge power x_{ESS} , EV battery charge power x_{EV} , PV generation power x_{PV} , and grid power x_{GRID} , which takes positive (negative) value in case of import (export):

$$x = \begin{bmatrix} x_{ESS} \\ x_{EV} \\ x_{PV} \\ x_{GRID} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

In this use case, the variables that describe the system state are SoC of ESS, SoC of EV's battery and position of EV (home or away):

$$s^t = \begin{bmatrix} s_{SoC,ESS}^t \\ s_{SoC,EV}^t \\ s_{pos}^t \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where s_{pos}^t is naturally binary i.e. 1 when the car is at home, 0 when the car is away. On the contrary, SoC is a continuous physical variable, which has to be discretized in the mathematical model of SDP.

The transition between ESS SoC values are deterministic and has to meet the following constraint. Below $\frac{\Delta T}{3600}$ term is the discretization step (in hours) that allows switching from energy to power domain as capacities are expressed in kWh.

$$s_{SoC,ESS}^{t+1} = s_{SoC,ESS}^t + x_{ESS} \frac{\Delta T}{3600} \frac{1}{E_{ESS,cap}} \quad (8)$$

Evolution of EV battery's SoC is deterministic only when the car is present at home. Otherwise, it is quasi-deterministic thanks to the assumption introduced in Eq. 3:

$$s_{SoC,EV}^{t+1} = s_{SoC,EV}^t + \frac{\Delta T}{3600} \begin{cases} x_{EV}, & s_{pos}^t = 1 \\ -P_{EV}, & s_{pos}^t = 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Stochastic relationship between position states in successive stages is suitable to model with Markov chains. Therefore, we express the transition probabilities from home to away state $p_{10}(t)$ and from home to home $p_{11}(t)$. As there are only two possibilities for a car at home, these probabilities are each other's complement:

$$\begin{aligned} p_{10}(t) &= p(s_{pos}^{t+1} = 0 | s_{pos}^t = 1) \\ p_{11}(t) &= p(s_{pos}^{t+1} = 1 | s_{pos}^t = 1) \\ p_{10}(t) + p_{11}(t) &= 1 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

PV output depends on the weather and is constrained by the PV potential ($P_{pv,max}^t$) of the particular instant according to the forecast.

EV charging power term is constrained by the charger's power limitation $P_{evch,max}^t$ and can take non-zero value only when the car is present at home i.e. s_{pos}^t equals one:

$$x_{PV} \leq P_{pv,max}^t \quad (11)$$

$$x_{EV} \leq P_{evch,max}^t s_{pos}^t \quad (12)$$

Following constraint represents the power balance that assures meeting the household electricity demand while charging the EV battery:

$$P_{dem}^t + x_{EV} = x_{PV} + x_{ESS} + x_{GRID} \quad (13)$$

The objective function of SDP problems consists of two parts. First part stands for the immediate cost of taken decision, which consists of two terms for the quadratic and linear factors, where Q is Hessian matrix and q is the gradient of the objective function. Note that quadratic factor is necessary in the minimum power exchange objective case, in order not to reward export (negative values of variable x_{GRID}). However, we used the quadratic representation for all objective functions for generality. Table 1 shows the parameters in different optimization objective cases. Second part associates the estimated future cost of taken decision:

$$\min_x \frac{1}{2} x^T Q x + c^T x + \sum_{w=1}^W p(w: s^{t+1} | s^t) v^{t+1}(s^{t+1}) \quad (14)$$

where w is one scenario from the scenario set W . Estimated future cost is the weighted sum of the values (cost) of the final state that can be reached accordingly. Here the weight is the probability of scenario w to happen, which ends up with final state s^{t+1} .

TABLE I. OBJECTIVE FUNCTION FOR THREE DIFFERENT EM TARGETS

Objective	Max PV	Min Bill	Min Exchange
Q	$\begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$	$\begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{vmatrix}$	$\begin{vmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2 \end{vmatrix}$
c^T	$[0 \ 0 \ P_{pv,max}^t \ 0]$	$[0 \ 0 \ 0 \ c_{price}^t]$	$[0 \ 0 \ 0 \ 0]$

Value of a state is the value of the objective function when the optimal decision is taken in a state. Equation 15 show the example when the objective is minimum power exchange, where x_{GRID}^* is the optimal power exchange with grid according to the optimization result:

$$v^t(s^t) = x_{GRID}^{*2} + \sum_{w=1}^W p(w: s^{t+1} | s^t) v^{t+1}(s^{t+1}) \quad (15)$$

SDP solution starts by assigning values to the final stage T states. Then, backward calculations starts at the last stage before the final ($T-1$). Because being at any state at the final stage has no intrinsic value or cost, we assigned zero as value every states at final stage s^T :

$$v^T = 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (16)$$

IV. IMPLEMENTATION INSIDE SOFW

The structure of the SOFW is presented in Fig. 3. The SOFW exposes a RESTful API, which allows the introduction of optimization models, the registry of data sources and control outputs, as well as to input commands that are sent to the framework.

In this way, the SOFW manages the incoming data received via a machine-to-machine Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol, in topics defined by the user. Internally this data is preprocessed and filtered, in order to fit

the necessary time resolution of the optimization model and to discard outliers. The filtered data is the input for the predictions, which are calculated using Long-Short-Term-Memory (LSTM) based deep learning algorithms [13] for short term forecasting directly from the real-time streaming data.

Figure 3. Structure of the SOFW

If the data source is specified to describe the uncertainty in the stochastic model, as for example the plug-in time and state-of-charge (SoC) of EVs, this information together with the timestamp are stored in the historical data repository. After a certain time period a new Gaussian distribution is calculated, allowing in this form a more precise calculation of the Markov model. In this case, the transition probability matrix of the Markov model become individual for each household, where SOFW is deployed.

SOFW allows the selection between three different open source solvers in charge of solving the optimization problem. The solvers are Glpk, Ipopt and Bonmin. All kind of linear, quadratic, mixed integer, non-linear and binary problems are addressed with these solvers.

The control outputs are also published to a MQTT broker. The user has to register to the topic, under which the optimization results are published. The results will work as set-points that can be used by drivers controlling the different machines. In S4G, for example, the set-points are used to control the charging/discharging of ESS, the charging of EVs, the output of the PV and the energy dispatch to/from the grid.

For starting the framework, the user has to choose the optimization horizon as total number of time steps and the time step size. The inputs of the data sources will be internally adjusted to this horizon resolution.

The core of the SOFW is the use of dynamic programming to solve the stochastic optimization problem in order to cope with uncertainties of the problem. The optimization model is entered by the user through the model endpoint. Optimization modeling language Pyomo is used for the mathematical definition of the problem.

Dynamic programming (DP) applied to an optimization problem partitions the problem into several sub-problems and solves them separately [14]. Each sub-problem has less variables than the original problem and therefore requires significantly less computational power to be solved. For this, the optimization horizon is broken into several decision stages and each stage is discretized into several number of states representing a unique system situation, as shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. SDP divides the optimization horizon into several stages (horizontal axis) and divides stages into several states (vertical axis).

Every single state establishes a unique optimization problem that can be solved independently from the peer states (different states of the same stage). For this reason, SOFW multi-instantiates the optimizer for a higher processing speed. Besides, the optimal decision at stage t depends also on the state to be reached at stage $t+1$ by this decision. In a Stochastic Dynamic Program, the optimal decision depends on the expected future cost, which is the weighted sum of the costs of future states that can be reached. The weights are the probabilities of relevant transitions. As the future stages' benefits (costs) are necessary for the optimization problems, SDP is computed by using backward induction, i.e. starting the calculation from the final stage, storing the future stage solution, and proceeding backwards.

SOFW uses a container technology for its development, which eases and makes its deployment more flexible. Shortly, SOFW has been deployed in debian-based operating systems such as raspbian for raspberry with ARM microprocessors and debian 9 for a server with AMD microprocessors.

V. TEST SCENARIO AND METHODOLOGY

We simulated a residential scenario to test the optimization approach formulated in section II. Central to this scenario is a household with grid connection in Italy. The house has rooftop PV panels with 7.6 kW nominal electric power under standard test conditions. Generation surplus can be fed to the grid or stored in an energy storage system with 9.6kWh energy capacity that can be charged/discharged through an inverter with maximum 6.4kW power. The household owner has an EV with 30kWh capacity, which is charged with a 3kW EV Charging Supply Equipment.

Due to the lack of sufficient measurement data, we adopted a statistical model to construct EV plug-in model. According to survey [15], departure-arrival times of residential cars show Gaussian distribution. Mean departure and arrival times are 7:19h and 18:45h. Standard deviations are 46min and 78min respectively. These parameters were used in a Monte-Carlo simulation to generate 10000 pairs of departure and arrival times. These samples were analyzed in order to calculate the Markov transition matrices.

Due to limited computational power, we set one-hour time resolution of SDP. The optimization horizon is set to 24 hours, therefore, there are 24 time steps of one hour. SDP is reconstructed at each hour with the shifted 24-h predictions.

Both ESS and EV's battery operations were constrained within 20-100% SoC range due to usage specifications. To perform SDP, we discretized the feasible SoC spaces with 10% resolution, so that SOC's can take values only from the set

$\{20,30,40,50,60,70,80,90,100\}$. Thus, the total number of small-optimization problems to be solved by SDP is 3888.

In this scenario, there is no communication between EV and charging equipment when the car is not present at home. However, SDP instance needs to be constructed even with the information when the car is away. Therefore, we construct the quasi-deterministic transition function of EV's SoC state, Eq. 9, based on the following assumption: when the EV is not at home, the EV would be consuming 3 kW average power so that SoC would decrease 10% with respect to the previous hour's level.

In order to measure the optimization performance in the sense of dealing with plug-in profile uncertainty, we designed five daily use scenarios. Driving and departure instants are different in each scenario where number of hours spent away is for now uniformly 10 (please see section VI for future work). Table II shows the departure-arrival instants of the tested scenarios.

Scenarios	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
Departure	05:00	06:00	07:00	08:00	09:00
Arrival	15:00	16:00	17:00	18:00	19:00

We simulated the scenarios on a sunny day, where PV generation potential exceeds the demand forecasts, as observed in Fig. 5. The SoC of both batteries, EV's battery and ESS, were assumed to be 30% at the beginning of the simulation. The price signal, with which the house purchase power is a variable price signal as shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5. Power generation-consumption forecasts and price

VI. RESULTS

The results of the operations are optimized according to three local energy management objectives, i.e. minimization of power exchange with the grid, minimization of power bill, maximization of PV utilization. The performance of this optimization approach was evaluated in regard to the ability to cope with EV plug-in time and EV's battery consumption uncertainty as well as the local energy management indicators. Because the uncertainties are calculated based on real-time EV's plug-in time and EV's SoC data, SOFW can be used in the future on the test site in Italy to collect this data and calculate the uncertainty needed in the optimization model.

The computations were done by executing the open-source optimization solver Bonmin on a computer with Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-4800MQ CPU 2.70 GHz processor. A new optimization problem with 24-hours horizon is reconstructed every hour with updated forecast and real-time data. As stated above, SDP divided 24-h problems into 3888 sub-problems, which are computed subsequently without using parallel computation. Average calculation time was 321 seconds for a complete optimization solution. These results show the feasibility of the optimization models within the SOFW.

Optimization with different objectives resulted in different EV charging control patterns. Fig. 6 illustrates the SoC change over time when scenario S3 (see table II) was tested. Results show that *bill minimization* is the objective that leaves the SoC at lowest level after charging in comparison with the other approaches. The other two objectives showed patterns similar to each other although the *maximum PV utilization model* stopped charging between 3am and 4am in order to shift the charging to when the PV generation is high.

Figure 6. EV's SoC Charging control patterns

Table III shows the performance of SDP model in different drive scenarios when optimized in terms of self-consumption, i.e. minimized power exchange with the grid. Results show that departures slightly earlier than expected do not lead to failure in meeting charging demand. The EV has to be charged at other locations only in case of extreme scenarios such as S1 in table II). This happens due to effort of shifting EV charging towards PV generation hours. For departures before 8am, the EV did not have enough energy to complete return drive, therefore needed to be charged at other locations.

TABLE III. PERFORMANCE IN DIFFERENT DRIVE SCENARIOS

Scenario	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
EV SoC at departure [%]	70	80	90	100	100
Charging at other location [kWh]	10	0	0	0	0
Import [kWh]	3.0	3.9	3.9	3.8	3.8
PV Utilization [%]	63	76	76	80	87

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This work presents a stochastic optimization framework and an approach to solve a residential EV charging problem from a use case of the S4G project. SOFW works with Stochastic Dynamic Programming and models the uncertainty of EV's plug-in time and SoC according to an inhomogeneous Markov

model. The approach was successfully tested on a standard desktop computer. The preliminary results are promising regarding local energy management targets and dealing with uncertainty in EV drive profiles. However, this approach is optimal to some limited use scenarios where simple assumptions on daily use hold true in general.

As next, higher-state resolution in dynamic programming optimization will be tested with parallel-computing techniques. Moreover, uncertainties due to EV's battery consumption will be included with different trip types and plug-in times. Besides, real data from the test site can be used for the EV plug-in model.

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